

THE EFFECT OF PENTAHHELIX ROLE AND DIGITAL MARKETING ON TOURISM DESTINATION IMAGE, TOURIST ATTRACTION, TOURISTS REVISIT INTEREST TO BATU CITY

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Abstract

This study aims to examine and analyze the influence of the role of pentahelix, digital marketing, image of tourist destinations and tourist attractions on the interest of returning tourists in Batu City. The population of this study is the population in this study are visitors to Batu City tourism object. A sample of 100 was selected using the Proportional Sampling technique. The hypothesis was tested using a structural equation model (SEM) with the help of the AMOS program. The results showed: (1) the role of pentahelix has a significant effect on the image of tourist destinations, (2) the role of pentahelix has a significant effect on tourist attraction, (3) the role of pentahelix has a significant effect on the interest of tourists to visit again, (4) digital marketing has a significant effect on the image of tourist destinations, (5) digital marketing has a significant effect on tourist attraction, (6) digital marketing has a significant effect on the interest of tourists to visit again. (7) The image of a tourist destination has a significant effect on the interest of tourists to visit again, (8) tourist attraction has a significant effect on the interest of tourists to visit again.

Keywords: The Role of Pentahelix, Digital Marketing, Image of Tourist Destinations, Tourist Attraction, Interest in Returning Tourists

1. INTRODUCTION

In developing nations like Indonesia, tourism has a lot of potential. Along with the areas of energy, infrastructure, maritime, and food, the tourism sector is listed as a priority sector for national growth (Franjaya & Prastiwi, 2020). Tourism is one of the joints of the nation's economic development and broad international interaction, because with tourism each country will recognize and be known from one another. The pandemic is a protracted experience that effectively kills movement and drives individuals to remain at home, a condition known as "the death of mobility." The effect on tourism is significant. According to current projections, 75 million tourism jobs are immediately at risk, and the sector will lose more than US\$2.1 trillion in revenue (WTTC, 2020). All air fleets are grounded, borders are closed, cruise liners are moored, and hotels, restaurants, and tourist attractions are shuttered. The system as a whole is physically impacted by the coronavirus epidemic, which poses a threat to the system's basic survival. Tourism performance in East Java in the last 5 years has also decreased, where the

data for 2020 consists of: (1) January to March normal conditions, (2) Mid-March to June Tourism business is closed), starting in July until december some tourism businesses are re-opening. For foreign visitors, the movement of tourists in 2020 has declined by 85.3% compared to 2019, while domestic visitors have decreased by 63.1%. 7,251,987 visitors, both domestic and foreign, visited in 2019, a fall of 2,437,878 in 2020, and 1,414,111 in 2021. (Source: Office of East Java Culture and Tourism (2021)).

There are numerous ideas that explain how consumer behavior influences purchase intention. These theories often focus on how behaviors are developed and what variables influence them. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) created by is one of the theories of individual behavior that is continuously being explored in numerous investigations (Ajzen, 1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), a study model based on generally recognized intention, can be used to forecast and explain a person's behavior to determine their intention to make a purchase (Indrawati, 2017:19). Interest is the motivation behind a person's attention-grabbing behavior toward other individuals or other items (Widagdyo, 2017). A person's mental state that specifies a strategy to be able to execute multiple acts within a particular length of time is interest in returning (Basiya and Rozak, 2012). Tourism will grow and develop if it has a high frequency of visits in each period. This high visit will last if old visitors who have visited the attraction make a return visit because of an interest in conditions, or certain factors that strengthen the intention of tourists to make an interest in visiting again.

In order to provide advantages and benefits to the community and the surrounding environment, it is necessary to drive the tourism system through optimizing the role of academic (academics), business, community, government, and media, or ABCGM. This is done by creating orchestrations and ensuring the quality of activities, facilities, services, creating experiences, and adding value for tourism benefits. The term "destination image" refers to a variety of visitor impressions, beliefs, and pictures of a certain location that include diverse tourist attractions and products from nearby locations. Pentahelix's synergy is anticipated to boost the reputation of tourist places. Researchers Attas, Rizal and Aqsa (2021) and Sotiriadis, Marios (2021) conducted a number of investigations, and the findings indicated that the pentahelix played a significant role in the perception of tourism locations.

The focus of Industry 4.0 in the tourism industry is on digital transformation and tourism. This article will go over how digital marketing is used in Bali's tourism business, which is driven by industry 4.0 and the attitudes of generations Y and Z. Consider generations Y and Z, who are living increasingly digital lifestyles and are referred to as always-connected travelers, which implies they are constantly linked no matter where they are. Using a smartphone or mobile, people can connect to each other at any time. According to Smith and Chaffey (2013: 15), the foundation of an e-business is digital marketing. Through e-marketing initiatives based on digital media like search engine marketing, online advertising, and affiliate marketing, a company can improve its understanding of its customers, add value to a product, widen its network of distributors, and boost sales. The research gap is shown in the research conducted by Kim & Song (2018) entitled Effects of media and destination image on the behavioral intention to visit the Hwacheon Sancheoneo Ice Festival, where the research results show that

social media does not have a significant effect on tourists' interest in visiting. Conducted by andriani et al (2017) with the research title Study on Destination Image, Satisfaction, Trust and Behavior Intention. The results of the study show that the image of a tourist destination has no significant effect on the intention to return. The main key to the success of this innovation is synergy and strong commitment among stakeholders in carrying out. The Penta Helix model is very useful for managing complexity based actor. Several opinions regarding the five actors in the Penta model Helix. However, the Penta Helix model is better known as a concept or formula ABCGM namely Academic, Business, Community, Government, and Media (Slamet et al, 2017).

The study's originality is based on research conducted by M Nuh et al., (2020), in this study to produce more complex tourism, where interacting environmental indicators must be addressed, in this study referring to tourists or visitors (travelers). Reviews of the attractions that visitors visit are a significant input from travelers. Thus, in this instance, in addition to examining how the penta helix works together, the research's innovation is examining how tourists are involved in the growth of the tourism industry. As a result, a traveler will add ABCGM+ to the ABCGM formula, which is a penta helix notion.

2. THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

According to Ribowo (2019), it is essential to optimize the roles of academia (academics), business, government, community, and media (media publications) in order to drive the tourism system and ensure the quality of activities, facilities, services, creating experiences, and value for tourism benefits in order to provide benefits and benefits to the community and the surrounding environment. The term "destination image" refers to a variety of visitor impressions, beliefs, and pictures of a certain location that include diverse tourist attractions and products from nearby locations. Pentahelix's synergy is anticipated to boost the reputation of tourist places. Hardianto, Muluk, and Wijaya (2019), Anne, Risal, and Aqsa (2019), and others did a number of studies (2020) Hahm et al., Attas, Hadi et al., Nainggolan (2020), (2020). The findings of Marios Sotiriadis' research, published in 2021, demonstrate that the pentahelix plays a substantial role on the perception of travel destinations.

The pentahelix model is a guide for creating synergy amongst connected organizations to support objectives as effectively as feasible (Soemaryani, 2016). In Halibas, Sibyan, and Maat (2017), Rampersad, Quester, and Troshani claim that pentahelix collaboration has a crucial part to play in advancing the aims of shared innovation and pentahelix's contribution to regional socio-economic advancement. It is necessary to promote the tourism system by maximizing the roles of academia (academics), business, government, community, and media (media publications) or ABCGM in order to create orchestration, ensure the quality of activities, facilities, services, and create experiences and values of tourism benefits in order to provide benefits and benefits to the community and the environment. Research that discusses the role of pentahelix on tourist attraction has been carried out by Jaroslaw Plichta, 2019, Kesgin et al, (2019), Woyo (2019), Agyeiwaah (2019) Siti et al (2020), Rahmanita, (2020), Dey, Mathew and Hua (2020) Alicia et al, (2021) where the results of their research show the influence of

the role of the pentahelix on tourist attraction.

According to Juwita et al. (2018), the Pentahelix approach is a tourism-related strategy that involves aspects of the community and non-profit organizations in order to actualize an innovation supported by already-existing resources and potential for tourism. The ABCGM approach is the name of the Pentahelix tourism strategy used in Indonesia (Academic, Business, Community, Government and Media). The dynamics of business world conditions are influenced by the company's internal and external environment which requires the right tools for assessment and monitoring and the potential for misunderstanding of strategy (Riyadi, Nugroho and Arif. 2021).

The Pentahelix partnership, also known as ABCGM (Academic, Business, Community, Government, and Media) lines of activity, is believed to accelerate the development of tourist towns' considerable potential, which is ultimately anticipated to raise interest in traveling to these locations (Panjaitan, Andjarwati, Sumiati dan Panjaitan, 2019).. The relationship between pentahelix collaboration on visiting interest and brand equity was investigated by Evren, Emine and akıcı (2019), Hasan, et al., (2019), Kumar et al., (2019), Ragab, Mahrous and Ahmed Ghoneim (2019), Li, Wang and Dong (2020), Huy, Diane and Newsome (2020), Kusumawati, Utomo and Sunarti (2020), Mohammed, Mahmoud and Hinson (2021) where the results of their research show that the role of pentahelix has an influence on increasing interest in visiting tourism.

Based on the description above, the following hypothesis is proposed:

- H1: Pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourism destination image in Batu City.
- H2: Pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourist attraction in Batu City.
- H3: Pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City.

According to Smith and Chaffey (2013:15), e-marketing activities based on digital media, such as search engine marketing, online advertising, and affiliate marketing, help a company get closer to and better understand its customers, add value to a product, widen its network of distributors, and boost sales. Marketers must demonstrate brand identity through the available channels of communication and brand touch in order for the image to become ingrained in the minds of consumers. Technology advancements, alterations in consumer behavior, and corporate innovation all have a significant impact on a product's brand equity, particularly in the travel and tourist industry. This is The Role of Digital Marketing in Tourism Product Brand Equity. Research conducted by Sharma and Nayak (2019), Willems, Brengman and Kerrebroeck (2019), Liu, Mo and Lam Ng (2020), Saini and Arasanmi (2020), Amaro, Barroco and Antunes (2020), Hasan et al., (2020) Rasoolimanesh et al (2021) Yuan et al., (2022) showed a significant influence between Digital Marketing and Image.

According to Smith and Chaffey (2013), the core of an e-business is e-marketing, also known as internet marketing or more commonly known as digital marketing? Through e-marketing activities based on digital media like marketing through search engines, online advertising, and affiliate marketing, a company can get closer to customers and understand them better, add

value to a product, expand distribution networks, and also increase sales. Research that discusses digital marketing on tourist attraction has been carried out by Kezia (2019), Pavlos and Weidenfeld (2019), Ballina, Valdes and Valle (2019), Xu et al., (2020) Ahmad Albattat (2020), Carlisle, Ivanov and Dijkmans (2020), Mihalic and Kircer (2020) where the results of their research show that there is an influence between digital marketing on tourist attraction.

Digital marketing, often known as online or electronic media marketing, is one strategy for promoting a tourism-related product with the goal of luring customers. In addition to drawing customers, it is typically utilized to increase a company's market and tell potential customers about popular tourist spots. Before visiting tourist destinations, the majority of prospective visitors will research their options. For instance, to learn about the location's accessibility via road, what amenities are offered there, and what events or activities are scheduled there. The use of social media to promote Indonesian tourism will increase the number of visitors to Indonesia. Research conducted by Girish Shrestha (2019), Amit and Gilitwala (2019) Ika and Sumarni (2019), Klaasvakumok and Kurniawati (2020) Khaled et al., (2020) shows a significant influence between Digital Marketing and interest in visiting.

Based on the description above, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Digital Marketing has a significant effect on tourism destination image in Batu City.

H5: Digital Marketing has a significant effect on tourist attraction in Batu City.

H6: Digital Marketing has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City.

Interest is the motivation behind a person's attention-grabbing behavior toward other individuals or other items (Widagdyo, 2017). A person's mental state that specifies a strategy to be able to execute multiple acts within a particular length of time is interest in returning (Basiya and Rozak, 2012). The image of a destination is critical in selling it to stakeholders, including tourists. An image is generated by a person's perception of a thing, not by the object itself. Advertisements, word of mouth, trips to tourist destinations, experiences derived from tourist destinations, and happiness with visits to destinations can all contribute to the construction of a tourist destination's image (Hailin et al., 2011). A destination image is a belief or knowledge about a person's assessment of a destination which is not always formed from experiences and facts during a tour which can be used as a driving factor for traveling. According to Hallmann et al., (2015) the image of a destination can be considered as the perception of tourists and sellers about the attributes or tourist objects available in a destination and plays an important role in the description, promotion, integration, and distribution of destination products. According to Asael (2013), destination image is defined as the overall perception of the destination which is formed by processing information from various sources from time to time. Thus, the image of a destination can be formed after someone obtains information or visits the destination. Research conducted by Yao, Chu and Kobori, 2017, Yunduk, Yu and Kim (2017), Jamaludin, Fauzi Mokhtar, Aziz (2018), Lee, Pan and Chung (2018), Juyeon, Kyungmo, Song (2018) Riyad et al., (2019), Foster and Sidharta, (2019), Kanwel et al (2019), Siregar et al, (2019), Zhang & Niyomsilp (2020), Afshardoost and Eshaghi (2020), Sintesa, Kurniawati, and Nata (2020), Ahmad et al., (2020), Gosal and Rahayu (2020),

Abbasi et al., (2020), Suzan and Soliman, (2020) show that the image of a destination has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest.

Based on the description above, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: Tourism destination image has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (1997), a product is anything that may be provided to a market to meet a want or need. The product is associated with an item or service provided by a certain company; the product or service in question here is a superior tourist attraction. The attractiveness of a product or service is said to attract customers if the product or service provides more value than the customer expects. Research conducted by Chien (2017), Arisara Seyanont (2017), Hongmei et al (2018), Yacob, Johannes and Qomariyah (2019) Utama and Purnama (2019), Yacob and Erida (2019), Ariesta, Sukotjo and Suleman, (2020), Bashar (2020), Nguyen (2020) show that there is an influence between tourist attraction and tourists revisit interest

Based on the description above, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H8: Tourist attraction has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest to Batu City.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

A quantitative descriptive method was used in the design of this investigation. The most critical area of any research is probably process analysis. The preference for an effective research method must be in accordance with the hypothesis (Riyadi, Slamet, 2019). Visitors to Batu City's tourist attractions make up the study's population, which is located there. Since the population size is unclear, the number of samples used in this study was derived using Paul Leedy's formula from Arikunto (2006), resulting in a sample size of 100 tourists. SEM (Structural Equation Modeling), which makes use of the AMOS 26 program, was the data analysis technique.

4. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Validity testing was carried out using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The validity test according to Sekaran (2006) aims to determine the fidelity and accuracy of a measuring instrument in carrying out its measuring function. Validity testing was carried out using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). According to Ghozali (2015), factor loading 0.50 is considered significant. The results of data processing show that all question items are declared valid, because each question item which is an indicator of each variable has been extracted perfectly and has a factor loading of 0.50.

To measure the reliability of this research instrument, it is done using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. The Cronbach Alpha value of each variable shows that the variables of pentahelix role, digital marketing, tourism destination image, tourist attraction, and tourists revisit interest have a Cronbach alpha coefficient > 0.6 which means the reliability is said to be good (Ghozali,

2015).

Hypothesis testing was conducted to determine the relationship between variables directly. In this study, it is expected that causality testing can determine the effect that occurs from the pentahelix role (X1) and digital marketing (X2) on tourists revisit interest (Y) with tourist destination image (Z1) and tourist attractions (Z2) as intervening variables. The results of the calculations are presented in the following table:

Table 1: Regression Weight Evaluation for Causality Test

Variabel		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Keterangan
Citra destinasi wisata (Z1)	<--- Peran pentahelix(X1)	0.320	0.092	3.481	0.000	Signifikan
Daya tarik wisata(Z2)	<--- Peran pentahelix(X1)	0.560	0.084	6.687	0.000	Signifikan
Minat berkunjung Kembali (Y)	<--- Peran pentahelix(X1)	0.427	0.093	4.601	0.000	Signifikan
Citra destinasi wisata (Z1)	<--- Digital marketing(X2)	0.534	0.127	4.189	0.000	Signifikan
Daya tarik wisata(Z2)	<--- Digital marketing(X2)	0.248	0.094	2.629	0.009	Signifikan
Minat berkunjung Kembali (Y)	<--- Digital marketing(X2)	0.193	0.094	2.064	0.039	Signifikan
Minat berkunjung Kembali (Y)	<--- Citra destinasi wisata (Z1)	0.232	0.084	2.756	0.006	Signifikan
Minat berkunjung Kembali (Y)	<--- Daya tarik wisata(Z2)	0.311	0.106	2.929	0.003	Signifikan

Source: Processed data collection results, 2022.

In the table above, statistical tests were carried out by observing the significance level of the relationship between variables indicated by C.R which was identical to the t-test in the regression and the probability value (P). A significant relationship is indicated by the C.R value greater than 1.96 and the P value less than 0.05.

4.1 Discussion

The Effect of Pentahelix Role on Destination Image

The results showed that pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourism destination image in Batu City. Thus, the hypothesis which states that pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourism destination image in Batu City is accepted. The positive influence explains empirically that the stronger the role of the pentahelix perceived by tourists, the better the image of the tourist destination, and vice versa, the weaker the role of the pentahelix perceived by tourists, the worse the image of the tourist destination. The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Hardianto, Muluk and Wijaya (2019); Anne, Risal and Aqsa (2020 ;) Attas, Hadi et al., (2020; Nainggolan (2020); Hahm et al (2020). Chamidah, et al., (2021); and Marios Sotiriadis, (2021); which states that there is a significant influence between the roles of pentahelix on the image of tourist destinations. The development of tourist destinations cannot stand alone, it requires strategies and supports one another. The application of the penta helix is needed in developing tourist destinations. This will facilitate the coordination, implementation and evaluation of the programs being organized. The penta helix strategy

between various tourism activists is needed for the implementation of the development of tourist destinations. The findings of this study are also capable and confirm of explaining the indicators that makeup the pentahelix, whose function in this study is gauged by 6 (six) indicators, namely: academics, business actors, communities, governments, media, and travelers (Visitors). The respondents had a positive impression of the pentahelix role variable based on the findings of the description analysis of all the indicators. The indicator with the greatest average score is the business actor, whereas the indicator with the lowest perception on the pentahelix variable is the government. In this example, it can be explained that the function of the tourist destination management in developing the tourism object is highly important to travelers while forming the pentahelix variable. Every facility and infrastructure that contributes to tourist comfort and the variety of tourism options available in this tourist location.

The Pentahelix Role theory from Lindmark (2012), the Destination Image from Lopes (2017), marketing management from Kottler & Keller (2016), and consumer behavior from Kotler & Armstrong can all be supported by the findings of this study (2016). Consumer behavior is described as the actions that consumers do to find, acquire, use, assess, and discard goods and services that they believe will meet their requirements. Consumer behavior includes all of the choices made before and after consumers take specific actions to acquire, use, and dispose of goods and services. Positioning is the process of creating an image, and a successful brand is one that has a solid position. The brand must first become well-known in order to have a strong brand position. The development of brand associations is based on brand recognition. A series known as brand image will emerge from many linked brand associations. A brand's reputation is influenced by consumer attitudes, perceptions, and beliefs. The better the brand's reputation, the more linked associations there are. The driving force behind the tourism system must be the optimization of the roles of academia (academics), business, government, community, media (media publications), and traveler or ABCGMT in creating orchestration and ensuring the quality of activities, facilities, services, creating experiences, and adding value for tourism benefits. The pentahelix's function will enhance a tourist destination's reputation by strengthening a variety of visitor perceptions, beliefs, and pictures of a place that offers a variety of goods and tourism-related features. Pentahelix's synergy is anticipated to boost the reputation of tourist places.

A destination's image is a critical factor in tourists' perceptions and evaluations of said destination. A destination image is a perception or understanding of a place and how visitors feel there. When the six pentahelix indicators are working as hard as possible to develop the destination, the destination's reputation as a tourism destination will improve. Academics expand studies to investigate tourism attributes that can improve image, the government supports every event that is held to strengthen the image of each tourist destination, media with quality news and increases its quantity, business people increase their investment to improve tourism, the community assists in providing space for development tourists, and travelers increase word of mouth towards these tourist destinations. If this is done consistently, the tourist destination's reputation will swiftly improve. Positive reviews of a destination increase the likelihood that visitors will return and suggest related locations to others.

The Effect of Pentahelix Role on Tourist Attraction

The results showed that pentahelix role had a positive and significant effect on tourist attraction. Thus, the hypothesis which states that pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourist attraction in Batu City is accepted. A positive influence indicates empirically that the stronger the role of the pentahelix felt by tourists, the stronger the tourist attraction will be, and vice versa, the weaker the tourist attraction will be.

The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Jaroslaw Plichta, (2019); Kesgin et al., (2019); Woyo (2019); Agyeiwaah (2019); Siti et al., (2020); Rahmanita, (2020); Dey, Mathew and Hua (2020); and Alicia et al., (2021) which states that there is a significant influence between the role of pentahelix on tourist attraction.

The Pentahelix Role theory from Lindmark (2012), the tourist attraction theory from Yoeti (2016), the marketing management theory from Kottler & Keller (2016), and the consumer behavior theory from Kotler & Armstrong can all be supported by the findings of this study (2016). In order to achieve shared innovation goals and advance regional socioeconomic development, the pentahelix collaboration is crucial. The government's support for the growth of the tourism industry is demonstrated by the sector's inclusion among the economic pillars, especially in terms of bringing in foreign exchange, boosting regional income and investment absorption, and lowering unemployment by creating a large number of new jobs. Given that numerous parties are involved and have an interest, the development of the tourism sector cannot solely depend on the government. A good pentahelix will boost visitor appeal as a whole. As a result, the administration of the tourism business requires synergy.

A tourist attraction is a place of interest that tourists visit, typically for its inherent or an exhibited natural or cultural value, historical significance, natural or built beauty, offering leisure and amusement. Anything that draws people to a certain location is considered a tourist attraction. In general, there are two categories into which tourist attractions can be divided: those that are created artificially and those that are naturally. For manufactured tourist attractions, the management must be innovative. The pentahelix plays a significant part in increasing man-made tourist attractions. Because artificial tourism can be developed and refined in response to visitor demand, it has a significant potential to continue to boost its appeal to tourists.

Actors in the tourism industry must be aware of the six pentahelix components in order to maximize their contribution to raising visitor appeal. If the tourist attraction grows, it will draw in more new visitors and/or encourage returning tourists because the attraction has changed.

The Effect of Pentahelix Role on Tourists Revisit Interest

The results showed that pentahelix role had a positive and significant effect on tourists revisit interest. Thus, the hypothesis which states that pentahelix role has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City is accepted. The positive influence explains empirically that the greater the function of the pentahelix perceived by visitors, the greater the tourists revisit interest, and vice versa, the lesser the role of the pentahelix perceived by tourists, the

lesser the tourists revisit interest.

The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Evren, Emine and akıç (2019); Hasan, et al., (2019); Kumar et al, (2019); Ragab, Mahrous and Ahmed Ghoneim (2019); Li, Wang and Dong (2020); Huy, Diane and Newsome (2020); Kusumawati, Utomo and Sunarti (2020), which stated that there was a significant influence between the role of the pentahelix on tourists revisit interest.

The Pentahelix theory from Lindmark (2012) and the revisiting interest theory from Kotler and Keller are both supported by the findings of this study (2016). The findings of this study also lend credence to several other theories, including the Theory Planned of Behavior (TPB) from Ajzen (1991), Marketing Management from Kottler & Keller (2016), and the theory of Consumer Behavior from Kotler & Armstrong (2016). The planned behavior hypothesis is predicated on the notion that people are logical beings who use information to the best of their ability. People consider the effects of their activities before deciding whether or not to engage in a certain conduct. The theory of planned behavior examines consumer perceptions of behavioral control, subjective norms, and consumer attitudes. Consumer attitudes gauge how a person views a product as beneficial or harmful, as well as positively or negatively.

If these tourism attributes are made available to consumers, it is likely that tourists will select these items as their travel destinations because of the attitude of consumers that tourists are expected to be able to choose tourist destinations in the future, which indicates that tourists are willing to accept or feel happy about these tourist destinations. Because visitors would take into account a lot of high engagement in the process of revisiting the tourist site, they are impacted by subjective norm variables in addition to one's attitude while picking tourism objects. Consequently, travelers will seek out more information on these tourism spots. If guests decide to return to the trip in this instance, the role of pentahelix in tourism development will be a major factor. Because most tourists have taken the tour as their first choice while choosing tourist attractions. Therefore, when visitors wish to return to a destination, they will search for the most recent information about the destination, changes that have taken place, and offers from the destination. Tourists in this situation will repeatedly seek information, weigh their options, select one option, and make a purchase in order to maintain their desire to return. Because it takes into account prior experiences that a person considers, behavioral control in this case refers to a circumstance when visitors perceive that an action is simple or difficult to complete.

The community, the government, and other stakeholders can all benefit from tourism growth in different ways. The economic health of a community may be impacted by how important tourism development is in a given area. Tourists who want to visit and observe the tourist area will be drawn to the area if it can manage a tourism area with regional features, such as culture. This is consistent with Suwantoro's assertion that the growth of tourism offers numerous advantages for the economic, social culture, and environment.

The growth of the tourism industry can spur the growth of other industries, increase the incomes of locals, and create new economic activities in a region. As a result, the pentahelix's

interactions between its components must be carefully optimized if tourism performance is to be improved in the current normal era.

The Effect of Digital Marketing on Tourism Destination Image

The results show that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on tourism destination image. Thus, the hypothesis which states that digital marketing has a significant effect on tourism destination image in Batu City is accepted. The positive influence empirically explains that the better the tourism digital marketing, the better the image of the tourist destination, and vice versa, the less tourism digital marketing, the poorer the image of the tourist destination. The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Sharma and Nayak (2019); Willems, Brengman and Kerrebroeck (2019); Liu, Mo and Lam Ng (2020); Saini and Arasanmi (2020); Amaro, Barroco and Antunes (2020); Hasan et al., (2020); Rasoolimanesh et al., (2021); and Yuan et al., (2022) showed a significant influence between digital marketing and the image of tourist destinations.

In this study, digital marketing is defined by 4 (four) indicators: interactive, incentive programs, site design, and cost. The findings of this survey show that respondents have a positive view of the indicators included in the digital marketing variable. The indication on the digital marketing variable that is seen to have the lowest value is cost, whereas the indicator on the incentive program receives the highest average value. This demonstrates that the incentive program, which includes the level of marketing efforts made by the administrator of this tourist social media account, special discounts for followers of tourist attractions on this social media account, and discounts for content-sharing on private platforms, is the indicator item that tourists pay the most attention to.

The findings of this study support the tourist destination image theory from Lopes and the digital marketing theory from Liesander (2017). (2017). The findings of this study also lend credence to several other theories, including the Theory Planned of Behavior (TPB) from Ajzen (1991), Marketing Management from Kotler & Keller (2016), and the theory of Consumer Behavior from Kotler & Armstrong (2016). The Theory Planned of Behavior (TPB) is frequently used to describe how an individual responds when doing a task or taking action depending on his/ her thinking. Tourists are a major determinant of decisions to do specific actions that would ultimately lead people to choose these tourist sites, according to consumer behavior in this scenario. According to TPB, an individual's behavioral intention or behavioral intention is influenced by a number of variables, including attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

The findings of this study show that tourists' perceptions of a site can be influenced by subjective norms. The manager of the tourist destination's digital marketing initiatives are to blame for the formation of this arbitrary standard. This refers to the belief about whether most people approve or disapprove of the behavior. It relates to a person's beliefs about whether peers and people of importance to the person think he or she should engage in the behavior. Subjective norms (NS) are factors that describe how each person perceives how society will support or not support them in carrying out a task or taking a certain action (Ajzen, 1991).

The core of an e-business is digital marketing. Through e-marketing activities based on digital media like marketing through search engines, online advertising, and affiliate marketing, a company can get closer to customers and understand them better, add value to a product, expand distribution networks, and also increase sales. Marketers must demonstrate brand identity through available channels of communication and brand touch for an image to become ingrained in consumers' brains. The public's opinion of a corporation or its products is known as its brand image. Technology advancements, alterations in consumer behavior, and corporate innovation all have a significant impact on a product's brand equity, particularly in the travel and tourist industry. This is where digital marketing comes into play.

The promotion of a tourism location has frequently used digital media. Social media content has a significant role in promoting travel and increasing the number of travelers through digital media. The social media material will improve the perception of tourism. Through smart social media marketing, new brands may be promoted, preferences can be formed, and the number of visitors to these tourist spots can increase.

Similar to products, tourist locations require marketing in order to draw customers. Through social media and websites, potential tourists look for information about travel destinations, lodging options, and other topics. Viewing the images or videos posted on social media will pique the attention and delight of potential travelers. Photos and videos that have been uploaded demonstrate how the offered content might entice potential tourists to use virtual services or go directly to the tourist site. The stronger the image of the place is in the eyes of visitors both new and returning tourists, the better the content developed for digital marketing.

The Effect of Digital Marketing on Tourist Attractions

The results show that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on tourist attraction. Thus, the hypothesis which states that digital marketing has a significant effect on the image of tourist destinations in Batu City is accepted. The positive influence explains empirically that the better the tourism manager's digital marketing, the greater the tourist attraction, and vice versa, the less application of digital marketing by the destination manager, the weaker the tourist attraction.

The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Kezia (2019); Pavlos and Weidenfeld (2019); Ballina, Valdes and Valle (2019); Xu et al., (2020) Ahmad Albattat (2020); Carlisle, Ivanov and Dijkmans (2020); and Mihalic and Kircer (2020) where the results of their research show that there is an influence between digital marketing on tourist attractions.

The findings of this study support the theories of digital marketing proposed by Liesander (2017) and tourism attractions proposed by Yoeti, Oka (2016). The findings of this study also support the consumer behavior theory from Kotler & Armstrong and the marketing management theory from Kottler & Keller (2016). (2016). Consumer behavior is essentially any action that leads consumers to ultimately decide whether or not to purchase a good or service. There is no doubt that Digital Marketing is used by so many businesses of different industries and has proven its worth in delivering many more leads to them. And of course, more leads mean more business, and more business means more profit. The travel industry is no

different and has adapted well to the realm of the digital world to increase their brands' awareness and be able to reach more possible customers as much as they could. The buying process is directly tied to consumer behavior. The search and research steps consumers use to assess a good or service are referred to as the buying process. Consumer behavior is also influenced by an item's or service's quality, pricing, and other factors including how well it works or is used. Through digital marketing campaigns run by destination managers for visitors, consumers, in this case, travelers will research information on these tourist spots. The tourist destination's tourist attraction will change as a result of this digital marketing.

In the advent of today's digital age, the importance of Digital Marketing for businesses has grown and the travel industry did not let this opportunity slip away. By going online, the travel business agencies can now implement different activities to make them known, reach a lot of people all over the world and tell them exclusive offers and post ads that will make every person watching want to head out and start planning for a getaway. Truly, the influence of Digital Marketing transcends borders which allowed the travel sector to entice people from all over the world to the different places they can visit.

The core of an e-business is digital marketing, also known as internet marketing. By engaging in e-marketing activities based on digital media, such as search engine marketing, online advertising, and affiliate marketing, a company can better understand its customers, add value to a product, expand its distribution networks, and boost sales. Digital marketing has a very broad range, combining technological, anthropological, humanist, and psychological elements through multimedia with robust and interactive capabilities. Utilizing IT, websites, social media, trends, netizens, business, online advertising, mobile applications, and other resources are all part of digital marketing activities. Given the enormous number of internet users in Indonesia, the development of digital marketing in the country is quite positive for the tourism industry.

The travel and tourism industry is undeniably one of the first that was affected as the world migrated to digitalization. The competition was all about coming up with the best strategy and utilizing it to make a successful trip and worthwhile experience for all their patrons. The better they do it, the more loyal patrons they can have and the more the profit increases. But of course, Digital Marketing does not only stop at making sure travelers can have the best pre-trip experience, it also covers in-flight and destination marketing. Digital Marketing is a guide for travelers to get the best of their travel experience.

Because people cannot be separated from devices connected to the internet and fast-paced lifestyles, the players in the tourism industry can market their products through advertising. This makes the promotion model very relevant to be applied to tourist destinations and tourism accommodation managers in order to present a positive image. Each favorable piece of content used in digital marketing will boost the area's reputation as a tourism attraction.

The Effect of Digital Marketing on Tourists' Revisit Interests

The results of the study show that digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on tourists revisit interest. Thus, the hypothesis which states that digital marketing has a significant

effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City is accepted. The results of this study also indicate a positive influence, explaining the positive influence explains empirically that the better digital marketing done by tourism managers, the higher the tourists revisit interest, and vice versa, the less digital marketing done by tourism managers, the tourists revisit interest.

The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Sumarlinah, Sukei, Sugiyanto (2022) Girish Shrestha (2019); Amit and Gilitwala (2019); Ika and Sumarni (2019); Klaasvakumok and Kurniawati (2020); and Khaled et al., (2020) show that there is a significant influence between digital marketing and tourists revisit interest.

The findings of this study confirm support the revisiting interest idea put forward by Kotler and Keller as well as the digital marketing theory of Liesander (2017). (2016). The findings of this study also lend credence to several other theories, including the Theory Planned of Behavior (TPB) from Ajzen (1991), Marketing Management from Kottler & Keller (2016), and the theory of Consumer Behavior from Kotler & Armstrong (2016). The marketing notion refers to a business's efforts to promote its goods so that consumers can purchase them. Through integrated marketing, marketing focuses on the target market point, customer needs, and methods for achieving the goals. Businesses earn from satisfied customers. In order for the attractions supplied by tourist sites to be in line with visitor preferences and be accepted by the target market, it is necessary for them to first understand the wants and aspirations of their patrons. Marketing is the analysis, planning, implementation, and control of programs created to generate, grow, and maintain productive and lucrative relationships with target markets with a view to attaining organizational goals, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2004:16). In essence, the introduction of demands marks the beginning of the purchasing process where customers identify a need or problem in order for consumers to truly experience the distinction between the actual situation and the desired one. Marketers must be aware of what consumers want in order for them to believe that their requirements are being addressed. Because consumers may express their needs and aspirations in this manner but do not take action, it is difficult to determine what these consumers' wants and requirements are.

If the target individual has a positive attitude toward the conduct, obtains acceptance from other individuals who are near to and related to the behavior, and believes that the behavior can be carried out properly, the individual has a high possibility of adopting the behavior. By including a variable, perceived behavioral control, to this construct. The notion of planned conduct is founded on the assumption that people are rational entities who use information in a methodical manner. People consider the consequences of their actions before deciding whether or not to engage in a certain conduct. The theory of planned behavior is a theory that examines consumer attitudes, subjective norms, and consumer perceptions of behavioral control. Consumer attitudes assess how a person perceives an object as favorable, negative, useful, or damaging. Consumer attitudes are believed to determine what will be done in the future, which means that if consumers are prepared to accept or feel glad about the product, it is most likely that the consumer will purchase it. Perceived behavioral control is a circumstance in which people believe that an action is easy or difficult to perform because it takes into account past experiences. Marketers must be able to comprehend their customers in this situation by

analyzing their everyday habits.

According to the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), behaviors are influenced by intentions, which are determined by three factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. It is also possible for external factors to directly force or prevent behaviors, regardless of the intention, depending on the degree to which a behavior is actually controlled by the individual, and the degree to which perceived behavioral control is an accurate measure of actual behavioral control. The Theory of Planned Behavior assumes that individuals act rationally, according to their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. These factors are not necessarily actively or consciously considered during decision-making, but form the backdrop for the decision-making process. In other words, people may not articulate a particular attitude, but it may nonetheless influence their decision-making. Research in this area aims to uncover these hidden values and ideas that influence decision-making. There is some controversy about the assumption of rationality because sometimes humans act emotionally, not rationally. Rather than saying humans behave rationally, some researchers call this "sense-making".

The behavioral intention element is still at the center of the Theory of Planned Behavior, but other factors, such as perceptions of behavior control, affect behavioral intention as well. However, it is believed that perceived behavioral control has both direct and indirect effects on forecasting customer behavior. The interaction between the three elements; attitudes, subjective standards, and perceived behavioral control becomes a determinant of interest that, in turn, determines whether the activity in issue will be carried out or not.

One form of promoting a travel or tourist product is through electronic media or the internet, using a variety of strategies or approaches to draw customers (Daud, 2021:105). In addition to drawing customers, it is typically utilized to increase a company's market and tell potential customers about popular tourist spots. Before visiting tourist destinations, the majority of prospective visitors will research their options. For instance, to learn about the location's accessibility via road, what amenities are offered there, and what events or activities are scheduled there. The use of social media to promote Indonesian tourism will increase the number of visitors to Indonesia.

The urge to return to an interesting location is the behavior of consumers who opt to visit or choose a tourist destination based on previous travel experiences. Interest in visiting is a result of previous visit experiences related to the quality of service for a country or region. The process of creating tourist visit intentions begins with a favorable performance in the form of a long-term outlook toward tourists.

A person's behavior can be changed by the very large digital footprint that digital marketing will leave in cyberspace. This is possible because visitors who continually view content that promotes the destination eventually develop a negative association with the location. In order to attract tourists, one must first evaluate their long-term performance. Due to the enjoyment and satisfaction of the visited object, visitors' desire to visit a tourist attraction is proof of visitor behavior. When a tourist returns to a tourist attraction after becoming interested in it, the tourist

will do a number of things, such as recommending it to others, wanting to go back again, constantly comparing the object to other tourist attractions, and picking the location of the object. Visitors to the tour, which is regarded as the best, look for information on the object from a variety of sources, including friends, family, and social media.

The Effect of Tourism Destination Image on Tourists' Revisit Interest

The results showed that the image of a tourist destination had a positive and significant effect on tourists revisit interest. Thus, the hypothesis which states that the image of a tourist destination has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City is accepted. The positive influence explains empirically that the desire to return as a tourist increases with the tourist destination's reputation, and vice versa, that the desire to return as a tourist decreases with the tourist destination's reputation. The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Yao, Chu and Kobori, 2017, Yunduk, Yu and Kim (2017), Jamaludin, Fauzi Mokhtar, Aziz (2018), Lee, Pan and Chung (2018); Juyeon, Kyungmo, Song (2018); Riyad et al., (2019); Foster and Sidharta(2019); Kanwel et al., (2019); Siregar et al., (2019); Zhang & Niyomsilp (2020); Afshardoost and Eshaghi (2020); Sintesa, Kurniawati, and Nata (2020); Ahmad et al., (2020); Gosal and Rahayu(2020); Abbasi et al., (2020); and Suzan and Soliman, (2020) show that the image of the destination has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest. Cognitive image, unique image, and affective image are the indicators in this study's perception of tourism sites. The variables included in the image variable of tourist sites are perceived favorably by the respondents, according to the study's findings. Unique image is the indicator with the highest average value, while the indicator for the tourist destination's image variable is seen as having the lowest value. This tour raises specific attractions that are different from other tours, this tour has a characteristic that makes us want to visit it, and this tour has a different impression from other similar tours. These are all ways to build a unique image. The findings of this study lend credence to Lopes' (2017) image theory of tourist locations, Kotler and Keller's (2016) theory of revisiting interest, and Ajzen's (2017) theory of planned behavior (TPB) (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior is employed in this study to understand the variables that affect accounting students' desire to engage in whistleblowing. The Theory of Planned Behavior is a development of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) which was previously proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975. According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) TPB explains that an individual's intention to behave is determined by three factors, namely: 1. Attitude toward the behavior 2. Subjective norm 3. Perception of Behavioral Control. Sulistimo (2012) asserts that a person's appraisal of a behavior when they witness it or are aware of it is their attitude toward it. The actions of a person will be evaluated by someone. An evaluation can be given that is either favorable or negative. According to Ajzen and Fishbein (2010), the greatest salient beliefs relate behavior to getting worthwhile consequences, which can be either positive or negative. The person will choose to act in his life according to his attitude toward the activity that he finds positive. In general, a person will act in a certain way that they believe will produce positive results (a positive attitude) as opposed to acting in a way that they think will produce negative effects (an unfavorable attitude). Behavioral beliefs are the assumptions that guide a person's attitude toward actions.

In order to promote their goods, tourism managers employ a variety of media, one of which includes an effort to project a positive image to customers. According to Simamora and Lim (2002) and Arista, brand image is an assessment of the sum of the many pieces of information customers have access to (2011:5). A good company's reputation is also inextricably linked to how customers perceive the products and services it offers. The customer is what is understood, and information is what is interpreted, claims Kotler (2005). The logo or symbol that a company uses to symbolize its goods can give insight into the firm's image. These symbols and logos not only set the company apart from similar rivals, but they can also convey the company's quality, vision, and mission. Customers who have a good attitude about the product are more likely to choose and purchase the chosen product, thus the corporation uses this image to pique consumer interest by trying to offer information that will later be interpreted (Suryani, 2008: 160). Consumer actions, such as evaluating an item he is interested in purchasing, are what shape the consumer's sentiments toward that item. The ability to evaluate something comprehensively and respond favorably or unfavorably to it is known as attitude. Customers who already have a favorable opinion of a product or brand will be more likely to purchase it. According to Bhaduri (2011:11), people's behavior is significantly influenced by their areas of interest. The phrase "purchasing interest" refers to the consumer's motivation for making a purchase decision and has a specific meaning. Consumers are more likely to choose a product or brand to buy when they have a positive perception of it. In Mahendrayasa (2014:2), interest serves as an impetus, or a powerful internal stimulant that drives behavior, where this urge is impacted by the stimuli and favorable thoughts about the product (Kotler, 2006:165). Customers will be encouraged and their buying interest will increase if the stimulus is strong and encouraging. On the other hand, if the stimulus or encouragement is weak and has no effect on the consumers' feelings, their buying interest will also be poor. Customers will be able to experience happy or pleasurable sentiments if the stimulus or encouragement supplied exceeds expectations, which will result in a larger buying interest. In contrast, if the buying interest is weak, consumers will choose other options before making a purchase decision.

The term "destination image" refers to a tourist's overall impression of a tourist location as well as their thoughts, beliefs, feelings, and perceptions of that destination. Selling a destination's image to stakeholders, particularly tourists, is crucial. A person's perception of an object determines how a picture is generated, not the other way around. Advertisements, word-of-mouth, trips to tourist locations, experiences created while visiting destinations, and interest in visiting destinations can all contribute to the construction of a destination's image. The way a person perceives a place will depend on how that place is portrayed, and this view can be shaped by advertising, the media, and a variety of other things. The idea of a destination picture as a representation of all subjective knowledge, preconceptions, imaginative ideas, and emotional feelings about a specific region. The confidence that visitors have in the goods or services they currently use or want to use will increase their willingness to return. The perception of a place is not always developed from experience or knowledge, but can also be shaped so that it serves as a powerful incentive for travelers to travel to a certain place.

The Effect of Tourist Attractions on Tourists' Revisit Interests

The results showed that tourist attraction has a positive and significant effect on tourists revisit interest. Thus, the hypothesis which states that tourist attraction has a significant effect on tourists revisit interest in Batu City is accepted. The positive influence explains experimentally that the stronger the tourist attraction, the higher the tourists revisit interest, and vice versa, the weaker the tourist attraction, the lower the tourists revisit interest. The results of this study directly support the research conducted by Chien (2017); Arisara Seyanont (2017); Hongmei et al., (2018); Yacob, Johannes and Qomariyah (2019); Utama and Purnama (2019); Yacob and Erida (2019); Ariesta, Sukotjo and Suleman (2020); Bashar (2020); and Nguyen (2020) show that there is an influence between tourist attraction and tourists revisit interest. The tourist attraction variable in this study is formed from 4 (four) indicators, namely: what can be seen (what to see), tourist activities that can be done (what to do), something that can be purchased (what to buy) and means of transportation (what to arrive). Based on the results of this study, it can be seen that the indicators contained in the tourist attraction variable obtain a good perception from the respondents. The indicator with the highest average value is the visible tourist attraction, while the indicator with the lowest perceived value is something that can be purchased. This demonstrates that tourist attractions that can be seen are the most important elements in travelers' desire to return. Many items that can be observed at this tourist area, Spot objects that can be visited there is not only one object, many special attractions on weekends and red dates are among the creating components.

The findings of this study lend support to the theories of Lopes (2017) regarding the perception of tourist sites, Kotler and Keller (2016) regarding the interest in returning, and Ajzen (1991) with the Theory Planned of Behavior (TPB). Some scholars claim that the notion of perceived behavioral control can be used to infer that people's perceptions of the ease or difficulty of displaying an attitude of interest are a key component of the notion of behavioral control. Therefore, if someone believes that a behavior is simple to demonstrate or carry out, they will have the intention to do so. According to Jogiyanto (2007), perceived behavioral control is defined as "the perceived ease or difficulty of doing the behavior" by Ajzen (1991). The way a person perceives behavioral control determines whether or not they believe the actions they take are the product of their own control. Behavioral control, according to Ghufroon (2010), is a personal ability in sensitivity to reading one's own circumstances and the environment. Additionally, the capacity to regulate and manage behavioral elements in accordance with circumstances and demands, as well as the propensity to draw attention and the need to modify behavior in order to appease others. Product image is very similar to brand image. The perceptions and the mental image associated with the product is called the product image. It is a set of beliefs related to a specific product. It signifies what the product currently stands for. It may refer to an infinite collection of previous historic facts, events, advertising and goals that work together to provide a mental impression on the public. A product's or service's image is a description of a thing as well as the perceptions and ideas that a person has about it. A favorable opinion that a tourism product creates in the minds of customers, both regular customers who frequently visit these attractions and potential customers who might visit these attractions. Customers who have a favorable opinion of a brand are more likely to make a

purchase. A positive tourism image will also stimulate consumer interest, which will make consumers interested in returning to the destination.

5. CONCLUSION

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), a study model based on generally recognized intention, can be used to forecast and explain a person's behavior to determine their intention to make a purchase (Indrawati, 2017:19). Similar to this study, it aims to expand on or apply the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to travelers in respect to how individuals act when determining whether or not to visit a tourist destination that is visited for the first time. To capture the interest of repeat visitors, the implementation of the TPB theoretical model in this study is deemed appropriate. All of the variables in this study, including the pentahelix's function, digital marketing, the perception of travel locations, and the popularity of tourist attractions, have been found to significantly affect travelers' desire to return. The study's findings demonstrate theoretical conclusions with the additional dimension of demonstrating how travelers are involved in the growth of the tourism industry. As a result, in order to describe the function of the pentahelix, a traveler will add the ABCGM formula, also known as ABCGM+.

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